

Ways of Improving the Personal Insurance Services in the Social Protection of the Population in Uzbekistan

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Abstract: In this article, it is considered the role of personal insurance in the social protection of the population in the Republic of Uzbekistan, proposals and recommendations aimed at improving the quality of personal insurance services by the insurance market professional participants to create various conveniences for customers and thus gaining their trust. Also, the work carried out by insurance companies, in particular, by Uzbekinvest insurance company, to increase the volume of services in the personal insurance market, was analyzed and conclusions were formed.

Key words: insurance, insurance market, insurance premium, insurance liability, insurance agreement, insurance coverage, accident, social protection, insurance culture.

Introduction. In countries with a developed insurance market, insurance serves as a part of social protection and personal insurance types take a leading place in it. The insurance network services are becoming more important as a source of investment for the economy. In the economy of countries based on market relations, the insurance market is one of the main source of investment resources. Insurance ensures sustainable development of the economy by preventing potential risks and compensating for damages.

Over the past six years, large-scale reforms have been implemented in our country under the leadership of Mr. Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In particular, in order to ensure the financial stability of the subjects of economic sectors, efforts were made to establish cooperation with leading foreign financial institutions, foreign investments were attracted to these areas, preferential credits were provided to business in exchange for existing investment opportunities in the country, and their number and scope of activity were expanded.

Also, in order to ensure the free operation of these entities, the existing legal and regulatory documents are being adapted to international and modern standards. At the same time, a number of new laws and regulations have been developed. Moreover, being considered as an integral part of the economy and important sector providing social protection of the population, large-scale reforms have been carried out in the last 6 years in the field of insurance in order to further develop the insurance market, such as, regulation and liberalization of the sector, making it attractive for investors, introduction of electronic insurance services and adoption of respective laws and by-laws. In particular, the adoption of the following legal acts serves as an important factor for the industry development: the new version of the Law "On Insurance Activities" dated by November 23, 2021¹, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4412 "On Measures to Reform the Insurance Market of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Ensure its Rapid Development" dated by August 2, 2019², Resolution of the President of the Republic of

¹ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Insurance Activities" dated by November 23, 2021

² Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4412 "On Measures to Reform the Insurance Market of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Ensure its Rapid Development" dated by August 2, 2019

Uzbekistan No. PQ-5265 "On Additional Measures for the Insurance Market Digitization and the Life Insurance Industry Development" dated by October 23, 2021³.

Research purpose and methods. The purpose of this research is to develop proposals and recommendations aimed at improving the provision of personal insurance services in Uzbekistan. Empirical and statistical analysis methods were used in the research.

Analysis and results. Currently, the changes taking place in the world and the globalization processes have different effects on the economic spheres and the social condition of the population. Climate changes observed in nature and various natural phenomena occurrences are increasing. All this leads to financial damage to economic sectors and humanity. In addition, in the process of using various modern technologies and technical tools in the production sectors, the probability of various types of accidents is increasing. The social importance of personal insurance in compensation of damage caused by accidents, occupational and other diseases related to workers and employees, as well as the population is high.

The insurance advantages to citizens and legal entities are widely promoted by the insurance market professional participants but these actions cannot be considered sufficient. Because the information about the insurance essence, its possibilities and benefits is not fully communicated to people in remote districts and rural areas and, as a result, they do not have complete understanding of insurance. Consequently, potential risks related to life, health and property of citizens remain uninsured, and when such incidents occur citizens are put in difficult situation and in such a situation they can rely only on the state support and people who show compassion. As an example, in April and May 2020, the unfavorable weather observed in Bukhara, Navoi and Samarkand regions of the republic as a result of natural phenomena (strong wind and heavy rain) and man-made disaster that occurred in the Sardoba reservoir of Syrdarya region caused a large amount of material damage to the health, housing, vehicles and livestock of the residents of these regions as well as to the property of organizations and business entities.

On April 27, 2020, as a result of a strong wind cyclone entering some regions of Bukhara region, 41,085 houses and 842 social objects were damaged causing great damage to the buildings roofs. As a result of this incident, only 12.0 billion soums (1.2 million US dollars) of damage to greenhouse farms were covered by insurance companies while the total loss amount was 140.0 billion soums (14.0 million US dollars). Other buildings had not been insured.

As a result of the man-made incident (water flood from the reservoir) in the Sardoba reservoir of the Syrdarya region, more than 70,000 people were affected by water in 3 districts of the region, in particular, 4,351 houses, 24 bridges and 276 kilometers of roads were submerged and as a result, some of them were completely destroyed and the rest were seriously damaged. Also, flood reached 5 villages of the neighboring Republic of Kazakhstan, and as a result, 845 houses were flooded and more than 31,000 residents had to be relocated. According to the calculations, the losses amounted to 1.5 trillion soums (150.0 million US dollars).

Following these events, 262 claims were received from residents and businessmen asking for compensation of losses caused to buildings and other properties insured by Uzbekinvest insurance company, and more than 5.77 bln. soums of insurance claims have been paid. From this, 3.55 billion soums were paid under 242 claims on natural disasters and 2.22 billion soums to 20 claims on man-made disaster⁴.

However, studies on this matter have shown that the majority of the population and business entities affected by natural and man-made events are not insured. As a result, many of the victims did not receive insurance protection, but were compensated by the state, which led to an increase in the budget cost burden.

³ Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-5265 "On Additional Measures for the Digitization of the Insurance Market and the Development of the Life Insurance Industry" dated by October 23, 2021

⁴ From Uzbekinvest EIIC JSC database for 2020 year

Witnessing the nature and usefulness of insurance services, the residents of these regions who received insurance companies' payment for the loss caused to the insured objects and citizens due to the above-mentioned natural and man-made events, increased their interest and confidence in insurance. As a result, they purchased insurance to insure their property and life for the next year.

Therefore, promoting the nature and benefits of insurance on a large scale is considered as one of the urgent issues in today's insurance sector, because in Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4412 "On Measures to Reform the Insurance Market of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Ensure its Rapid Development" this issue is one of the priority tasks.

In addition, this decree defines such tasks as introducing modern and advanced foreign models into the sphere, applying innovative ideas to increase the quality and speed of services, and increasing the personnel qualification in the field, enriching their knowledge and skills based on international experiences, and organizing their studies abroad.

On April 18, 2022, the head of our state Mr. Shavkat Mirziyoyev paid serious attention to the issue of social protection of the population in an open dialogue with medicine personnel on the topic of "Reforms in medicine - for human dignity". In the dialogue, it was proposed to make changes to the Constitution to develop medical insurance forms, to entrust the state with the obligation to cover damage caused to citizens' health by ecology, and to ensure the high status of medical workers, and to start this experience first in Syrdarya region and then gradually introduce it in all regions after taking necessary preparations⁵.

In order to ensure the execution of the above-mentioned tasks, Uzbekinvest Export-Import Insurance Company JSC is implementing a number of activities. The company has developed special programs for 2022, in particular, to set cooperation with neighborhoods ("with mahalla"). Uzbekinvest has started activities for working in the neighborhood system.

It is known that in Uzbekistan, the role of self-management, that is, neighborhood assembly in society is important. Uzbekinvest insurance company is organizing relevant activities in order to increase the insurance services volume in order to cover the population with insurance. In particular, meetings, roundtable discussions and presentations are being held for people and employees of large enterprises and students of higher education institutions, visits are made to different houses, primarily to provide understanding about insurance and explain the insurance benefits.

Currently, insurance market professional participants must expand these activities in terms of quantity and quality in order to increase the interest of clients in insurance and the volume of services.

The implementation of the above measures in the insurance market ensures positive changes in insurance indicators in the republic. For example, let's consider the results of insurance companies in the republic in 2018-2022 in relation to accident insurance.

Picture 1. Contracts concluded and obligations accepted by insurance companies under accident insurance in 2018-2022⁶

⁵ Gazeta.uz - news portal.

https://www.gazeta.uz/uz/2022/03/18/constitution/?utm_source=push&utm_medium=telegram.

⁶ Prepared by the author based on the information of the IMDA.UZ site

Picture 2. Insurance premiums and claims paid under accident insurance agreements concluded by insurance companies in 2018-2022⁷

When we analyze Pictures 1 and 2, according to Picture 1, there was a decrease in the number of insurance contracts concluded in 2019 and 2020. When looking at Picture 2, the amount of insurance claims paid to customers in 2018, 2019 and 2021 increased significantly which is due to inefficient underwriting work. As a result, the company had to change its current underwriting policy which led to a decrease in the number of insurance contracts concluded in 2020-2021. It must be noted that this situation was caused by the COVID-19 pandemic that started in 2020⁸.

However, on the basis of these graphs, it is possible to see another situation. Although the number of contracts decreased during this period, the level of customers social protection by insurance increased, meaning that insurance obligations of insurance organization went up, and, in turn, the amount of insurance claims for the damage caused also increased.

This trend is remaining from year to year, in other words, the number of customers, insurance premiums and insurance claims paid rise the importance of insurance as a social protection and lead to the customers' trust in insurance services and a positive change in their opinions on insurance.

If we look at the example of Uzbekinvest insurance company (Pictures 3-4), it can be seen that the indicators are growing as a result of the efforts made by the company in 2018-2022.

Picture 3. Contracts concluded and obligations accepted under accident insurance by Uzbekinvest insurance company in 2018-2022⁹

⁷ Prepared by the author based on the information of the IMDA.UZ site

⁸ From the database of the Insurance Market Development Agency under the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan (according to the 2021 report). <https://imda.uz/uz/2021-yillik-korsattjika/>

⁹ Prepared by the author based on the information of Uzbekinvest insurance company

Picture 4: Insurance premiums and claims paid under accident insurance agreements concluded by Uzbekinvest insurance company in 2018-2022¹⁰

Pictures 3 and 4 show a trend of continuous growth of gross premium written and insurance claims paid for five years under accident insurance at Uzbekinvest insurance company¹¹. In particular, although the number of insurance agreements in 2022 constituted 68% of the numbers in 2021, as a result of the improvement of the insured's portfolio quality and customer demands growth, the amount of insurance obligations increased by 136%, the amount of insurance claims paid decreased by 86%. Together with the indicators of insurance obligations accepted insurance premiums have also grown by 127%.

Conclusion and suggestions. Although the market potential is sufficient to further improve the results indicated above and to expand the population coverage with insurance services, however, a large part of the population that can be insured in the republic is not yet insured. For this, insurance companies and the large number of existing insurance agents need to carry out consistent marketing and advertising activities, focusing especially on remote areas and densely populated centers.

Taking into account that today there are rapid changes and development in all areas of the world, in order to develop the insurance market of our republic, we believe that it is necessary to organize the following by the insurance market professional participants to develop services for the personal insurance types which play an important role in increasing the population coverage by insurance:

- constant hosting of public events aimed at raising the insurance culture and legal knowledge by the population and private and small businesses, to explain the insurance benefits by launching social advertising and distributing it to the population via Internet and social networks and through mass media;
- fundamental improvement of the system of timely and full insurance claims payment to the population and ensuring transparency in this regard, including the introduction of electronic services in this direction, digitalization in this field, and increasing customer awareness;
- insurance market digitalization with dynamic images and mass transition to modern online services, including the establishment and development of the "Face ID" system, creation of a system of continuous improvement of knowledge and skills of insurance market professional participants, in particular, teaching advanced foreign experience;
- in order to change the population attitude to insurance services, improving and simplifying insurance tariffs and their conditions, including, creating a system of personal insurance types actuarial analysis and the insurance products underwriting modernization, keeping actuarial account books based on innovative ideas and applying advanced and modern experiences to it;

¹⁰ Prepared by the author based on the information of Uzbekinvest insurance company

¹¹ Unified automated information system of Uzbekinvest EIIC JSC (<https://uzbekinvest.uz/>) (according to 2021 report)

- in order to reduce the factors preventing insurance sector development, to further increase the insurance services quality based on market requirements and to ensure transparency, to introduce electronic services on the basis of national legislation, to develop new modern insurance products and to modernize existing ones based on market demand and world experience.

It would be appropriate to ensure the participation of the state in the issues proposed above and to develop special state programs. In order to increase the efficiency of these activities, it is very important to develop new modern insurance products meeting the market requirements and take measures to promptly pay for losses to the customers resulted from the insurance event. It is important that the actions to be carried out show the insurance true nature and its advantages and serve to gain the customers trust.

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